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SECURITY & PRIVACY THREATS, ATTACKS AND COUNTERMEASURES IN INTERNET OF THINGS

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ABSTRACT

The idea to connect everything to anything and at any point of time is what vaguely defines the concept of the Internet of Things (IoT). The IoT is not only about providing connectivity but also facilitating interaction among these connected things. Though the term IoT was introduced in 1999 but has drawn significant attention during the past few years, the pace at which new devices are being integrated into the system will profoundly impact the world in a good way but also poses some severe queries about security and privacy. IoT in its current form is susceptible to a multitudinous set of attacks. One of the most significant concerns of IoT is to provide security assurance for the data exchange because data is vulnerable to some attacks by the attackers at each layer of IoT. The IoT has a layered structure where each layer provides a service. The security needs vary from layer to layer as each layer serves a different purpose. This paper aims to analyze the various security and privacy threats related to IoT. Some attacks have been discussed along with some existing and proposed countermeasures.

KEYWORDS

Internet of Things, privacy, attacks, security, threats, protocols.

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A NOVEL IMAGE ENCRYPTION SCHEME WITH HUFFMAN ENCODING AND STEGANOGRAPHY TECHNIQUE

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ABSTRACT

In today's day and age when everything is done with the aid of computing technology, the need for confidential communication has drastically increased. Not only the sensitive data such as top intelligent secrets of our nation but personal information of common people needs to be secure. Several combinations of cryptography and steganography techniques in different ways are used by researchers over the past to protect the data being transmitted. Cryptography uses mathematical algorithms to convert the data into an incomprehensible form and Steganography, on the other hand hides the data in a carrier such as image, data, audio or video. Cryptography provides necessary mechanisms for providing accountability, accuracy and confidentiality in public communication mediums such as the Internet and steganography is used in other fields such as copyright, preventing e-document forging etc. We are of the opinion that this security mechanism can further be increased by incorporating the use of Huffman coding in order to reduce the data length. This paper is an effort in the direction to hide, secure and compress the data. It explains the executed procedure by applying various encryption techniques one by one and our aim is to get the best security out of the existing ones. The proposed technique is implemented in MATLAB2016a and the results shown in this paper that our technique is better approach than the conventional techniques.

KEYWORDS

Cryptography; Steganography; Huffman Coding; Data Compression.

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AUTHENTICATION MECHANISM ENHANCEMENT UTILISING SECURE REPOSITORY FOR PASSWORDLESS HANDSHAKE

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ABSTRACT

In this paper the idea of an enhanced security authentication procedure is presented. This procedure prohibits the transmission of the user's password over the network while still providing the same authentication service. To achieve that, Kerberos Protocol and a secure password repository are adopted, namely a smart card. The conditional access to a smart card system provides a secure place to keep credentials safe. Then, by referencing to them through identifiers, an authentication system may perform its scope without revealing the secrets at all. This elevates the trustworthiness of the mechanism while at the same time it achieves to reduce the overhead of the authentication systems due to the elaborate encryptions procedures.

KEYWORDS

Kerberos v5, LDAP, authentication, password handling, smart card

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MINING PATTERNS OF SEQUENTIAL MALICIOUS APIS TO DETECT MALWARE

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ABSTRACT

In the era of information technology and connected world, detecting malware has been a major security concern for individuals, companies and even for states. The New generation of malware samples upgraded with advanced protection mechanism such as packing, and obfuscation frustrate anti-virus solutions. API call analysis is used to identify suspicious malicious behavior thanks to its description capability of a software functionality. In this paper, we propose an effective and efficient malware detection method that uses sequential pattern mining algorithm to discover representative and discriminative API call patterns. Then, we apply three machine learning algorithms to classify malware samples. Based on the experimental results, the proposed method assures favorable results with 0.999 F-measure on a dataset including 8152 malware samples belonging to 16 families and 523 benign samples.

KEYWORDS

Android, Malware, Frequent Sequence Mining, Behavioural Pattern, API Calls, Dynamic Analysis

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CO-OPERATIVE WIRELESS INTRUSION DETECTION SYSTEM USING MIBS FROM SNMP

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ABSTRACT

In emerging technology of Internet, security issues are becoming more challenging. In case of wired LAN it is somewhat in control, but in case of wireless networks due to exponential growth in attacks, it has made difficult to detect such security loopholes. Wireless network security is being addressed using firewalls, encryption techniques and wired IDS (Intrusion Detection System) methods. But the approaches which were used in wired network were not successful in producing effective results for wireless networks. It is so because of features of wireless network such as open medium, dynamic changing topology, cooperative algorithms, lack of centralized monitoring and management point, and lack of a clear line of defense etc. So, there is need for new approach which will efficiently detect intrusion in wireless network. Efficiency can be achieved by implementing distributive, co-operative based, multi-agent IDS. The proposed system supports all these three features. It includes mobile agents for intrusion detection which uses SNMP (Simple network Management Protocol) and MIB (Management Information Base) variables for mobile wireless networks.

KEYWORDS

Multi- agent, MIB, SNMP, Security

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THE NEW AGE OF COMPUTER VIRUS AND THEIR DETECTION

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ABSTRACT

This paper presents a general overview on computer viruses and defensive techniques. Computer virus writers commonly use metamorphic techniques to produce viruses that change their internal structure on each infection. On the other hand, anti-virus technologies continually follow the virus tricks and methodologies to overcome their threats. In this paper, anti-virus experts design and develop new methodologies to make them stronger, more and more, every day. The purpose of this paper is to review these methodologies and outline their strengths and weaknesses to encourage those are interested in more investigation on these areas. In this paper, first analyze four virus creation kits to determine the degree of metamorphism provided by each and able to precisely quantify the degree of metamorphism produced by these virus generators. While the best generator, the Next Generation Virus Creation Kit (NGVCK), produces virus variants that differ greatly from one another, the other three generators examined are much less effective.

KEYWORDS

Antivirus Techniques, Computer Antivirus, Creation, Defensive, Metamorphism, NGVCK, Virus.

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SURVEY AND TAXONOMY OF KEY MANAGEMENT PROTOCOLS FOR WIRED AND WIRELESS NETWORKS

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ABSTRACT

The purpose of this paper is to survey the key management protocols for wired and wireless networks and study their security aspects in terms of key generation, agreement and distribution. The central research challenge is exhaustive survey of secure and efficient key management protocols. In this survey, it is shown that all these protocols could be placed under one of two key management protocol categories: (i) peer to peer communication and (ii) group communication. This can also be analyzed that peer to peer key management can be classified as: (i) symmetric key, (ii) asymmetric key and (iii) hybrid key management protocols and group communication can further be classified as: (i) Diffie-Hellman based (ii)Hybrid key management. We can say that our theoretical and execution analysis of protocols emphasise various observations that can motivate researchers in key management issues of networks.

KEYWORDS

Key Management Protocols, Peer to Peer, Group, Multicast, Hierarchical, Tree based, Trusted Third Party, Escrow less, Server based, Server less

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ARCHITECTURE FOR INTRUSION DETECTION SYSTEM WITH FAULT TOLERANCE USING MOBILE AGENT

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ABSTRACT

This paper is a survey of the work, done for making an IDS fault tolerant. Architecture of IDS that uses mobile Agent provides higher scalability. Mobile Agent uses Platform for detecting Intrusions using filter Agent, co-relater agent, Interpreter agent and rule database. When server (IDS Monitor) goes down, other hosts based on priority takes Ownership. This architecture uses decentralized collection and analysis for identifying Intrusion. Rule sets are fed based on user-behaviour or applicationbehaviour. This paper suggests that intrusion detection system (IDS) must be fault tolerant; otherwise, the intruder may first subvert the IDS then attack the target system at will.

KEYWORDS

Fault tolerance, Mobile Agent, Intrusion Detection System

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IOT AND SECURITY-PRIVACY CONCERNS: A SYSTEMATIC MAPPING STUDY

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ABSTRACT

The increase of smart devices has accelerated sensitive data exchange on the Internet using most of the time unsecured channels. Since a massive use of RFID (Radio-frequency Identification) tags in the transportation and construction industries from 1980 to 1990, with the expanded use of the Internet with 2G/3G or 4G since 2000, we are witnessing a new era of connected objects. A huge number of heterogeneous sensors may collect and dispatch sensitive data from an endpoint to worldwide network on the Internet. Privacy concerns in IOT remain important issues in the research. In this paper, we aim to evaluate current research state related to privacy and security in IOT by identifying existing approaches and publications trends. Therefore, we have conducted a systematic mapping study using automated searches from selected relevant academics databases. The result of this mapping highlights research type and contribution in different facets and research activities trends in the topic of “security and privacy” in IoT edge, cloud and fog environment.

KEYWORDS

Internet of Thing, privacy, security, the mapping study

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TRUST BASED SCHEME FOR QOS ASSURANCE IN MOBILE AD-HOC NETWORKS

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ABSTRACT

A mobile ad-hoc network (MANET) is a peer-to-peer wireless network where nodes can communicate with each other without the use of infrastructure such as access points or base stations. These networks are self-configuring, capable of self-directed operation and hastily deployable. Nodes cooperate to provide connectivity, operates without centralized administration. Nodes are itinerant, topology can be very dynamic and nodes must be able to relay traffic since communicating nodes might be out of range. The dynamic nature of MANET makes network open to attacks and unreliability. Routing is always the most significant part for any networks. Each node should not only work for itself, but should be cooperative with other nodes. Node misbehaviour due to selfish or malicious intention could significantly degrade the performance of MANET. The Qos parameters like PDR, throughput and delay are affected directly due to such misbehaving nodes. We focus on trust management framework, which is intended to cope with misbehaviour problem of node and increase the performance of MANETs. A trust-based system can be used to track this misbehaving of nodes, spot them and isolate them from routing and provide reliability. In this paper a Trust Based Reliable AODV [TBRAODV] protocol is presented which implements a trust value for each node. For every node trust value is calculated and based trust value nodes are allowed to participate in routing or else identified to become a misbehaving node. This enhances reliability in AODV routing and results in increase of PDR, decrease in delay and throughput is maintained. This work is implemented and simulated on NS-2. Based on simulation results, the proposed protocol provides more consistent and reliable data transfer compared with general AODV, if there are misbehaving nodes in the MANET.

KEYWORDS

Ad-hoc, AODV, TBRAODV, MANET, Trust, Misbehaving node, Qos

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